

An ERA Governance Fit for Purpose

Science Europe Position on the Involvement of Stakeholders in the ERA Governance

Brussels, 22 November 2021

1. In line with Science Europe's continued involvement in building the [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#), this paper provides Science Europe's proposal on ERA Governance.
2. Science Europe appreciates the efforts of the ERA Forum for Transition, European Commission, and Council towards the development of the [Pact for Research and Innovation](#), ERA Governance, and ERA Policy Agenda.
3. Science Europe, bringing forward the perspective of the major national research performing and research funding organisations, supports the development of a strong and effective ERA governance. It therefore welcomes the [commitments](#) by the European Commission and Slovenian Presidency of the EU Council to include research stakeholders in the ERA Forum.

Stakeholders need to be meaningfully involved in the ERA Forum

4. Science Europe welcomes the [draft Council Conclusions](#), which foresee the regular, structured, and systematic long-term involvement of stakeholders in the ERA governance. Science Europe believes that the most effective and appropriate way to do so is to give them an advisory role to the ERA Forum. This approach would create a unified and efficient mechanism to manage the exchanges between stakeholders, the European Commission, and the Member States.
5. Science Europe, therefore, calls on the Council of the European Union and the European Commission to take the necessary steps to guarantee stakeholders the following:
 - Representation in the relevant meetings of the ERA Forum.
 - Contributing to the ERA Forum activities that will aim to implement the ERA Policy Agenda, including through inputs to policy documents where relevant.
 - Sufficient time to consult their membership, to the extent permitted by the policy processes.
6. Pan-European R&I stakeholders represent diverse communities whose memberships go beyond the EU. As a result, and to make the discussions as effective as possible, Science Europe considers it beneficial for stakeholders to indicate the strategic issues on which they can contribute the most.

Issues on which Science Europe considers its engagement crucial

7. Science Europe is furthermore determined to play its part in making this a success. To that end, it commits itself to:
 - Actively and constructively participate in all the relevant discussions in a timely fashion.
 - Consult its membership to bring the collective views of research funding and research performing organisations where appropriate.
8. Science Europe considers that a series of core issues exist where the involvement of stakeholders is essential to any discussion that would take place in the ERA Forum and would greatly benefit the advancement of the ERA. These core issues are:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science • Research assessment • Academic freedom • Research infrastructures • Research integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International and Cross-border collaboration • Equality, diversity, and inclusion • Research careers • Green and digital transitions
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The ERA would greatly benefit from the involvement of stakeholders in its governance

9. Pan-European stakeholders represent the organisations and bodies that implement the ERA on the ground and support a thriving research ecosystem. National research funders and research performers, as well as universities, play a fundamental role in its development.
10. To deliver policies and actions that can be implemented to advance the ERA, policy makers will need to harness the knowledge and expertise from all sectors. Research stakeholders are uniquely positioned to bring a long-term perspective on the ERA and connect EU decision makers to the organisations where that expertise is located at the national level.
11. Science Europe and its members drive the development of research policies, influence national research systems, and build strong national research ecosystems. Science Europe builds on the broad expertise and collective knowledge held by its Member Organisations to collectively drive European and international R&I policy developments.

About Science Europe

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking research in Europe. It brings together the expertise of 38 of the largest and best-known research organisations to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society. They collectively invest over €23.9 billion each year on research in 28 European countries.

Science Europe advocates science and the scientific community to help build the European Research Area (ERA) building upon the national research policies that its members develop, manage, and implement to create the best possible conditions for research.